

INHIBITING BACTERIAL HEME TRANSPORT USING DE NOVO DESIGNED PROTEINS

Dr. Rhys Grinter

Inhibiting heme piracy by pathogenic *Escherichia coli* using de novo-designed proteins

Received: 17 January 2025

Accepted: 29 May 2025

Published online: 09 July 2025

 Check for updates

Daniel R. Fox ⁴,
Ashleigh Kropp^{1,2}, Christopher J. Lupton ⁴, Kevin Lim⁵, Chunxiao Wang³,
Hari Venugopal ⁴ ✉ &
Rhys Grinter ^{1,2,3} ✉

Iron is an essential nutrient for most bacteria and is often growth-limiting during infection, due to the host sequestering free iron as part of the innate immune response. To obtain the iron required for growth, many bacterial pathogens encode transporters capable of extracting the iron-containing cofactor heme directly from host proteins. Pathogenic *E. coli* and *Shigella spp.* produce the outer membrane transporter ChvA, which binds host hemoglobin

IMPORTANCE OF ChuA IN PATHOGENIC *E. coli*

E. coli is one of the most significant bacterial pathogens. It is the main cause of urinary tract infections, and a significant cause of serious gastrointestinal infections.

ChuA is a TonB-dependent transporter produced by pathogenic *E. coli* that imports the iron-containing cofactor heme.

Heme is an important source of the essential nutrient iron during infection, making ChuA an important virulence factor during systemic infection.

ENGINEERING A ChuA-DEPENDENT REPORTER STRAIN

ChuA TARGETS HEMOGLOBIN WITH HIGH AFFINITY

Daniel Fox

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

ChuA TARGETS HEMOGLOBIN WITH HIGH AFFINITY

Daniel Fox

$\alpha\beta$ -Hemoglobin steady-state kinetics

ChuA EXTRACTS HEME FROM HEMOGLOBIN

Daniel Fox

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

ChuA TARGETS HEMOGLOBIN WITH HIGH AFFINITY

Daniel Fox

pH and Redox State
Dependent

Hemoglobin
Tetramer

Hemoglobin
Dimer

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

ChuA TARGETS HEMOGLOBIN WITH HIGH AFFINITY

Daniel Fox

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

ChuA TARGETS HEMOGLOBIN WITH HIGH AFFINITY

Daniel Fox

HIS-86 AND HIS-420 CONTRIBUTE TO HEME COORDINATION

Daniel Fox

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

A MODEL FOR HEME EXTRACTION BY ChuA

Daniel Fox

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

INHIBITING Ch_uA USING DE NOVO DESIGNED BINDERS

Article

De novo design of protein structure and function with RFdiffusion

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06415-8>

Received: 14 December 2022

Accepted: 7 July 2023

Published online: 11 July 2023

Open access

 Check for updates

Joseph L. Watson^{1,2,15}, David Juergens^{1,2,3,15}, Nathaniel R. Bennett^{1,2,3,15}, Brian L. Trippe^{2,4,5,15}, Jason Yim^{2,6,15}, Helen E. Eisenach^{1,2,15}, Woody Ahern^{1,2,7,15}, Andrew J. Borst^{1,2}, Robert J. Ragotte^{1,2}, Lukas F. Milles^{1,2}, Basile I. M. Wicky^{1,2}, Nikita Hanikel^{1,2}, Samuel J. Pellock^{1,2}, Alexis Courbet^{1,2,8}, William Sheffler^{1,2}, Jue Wang^{1,2}, Preetham Venkatesh^{1,2,9}, Isaac Sappington^{1,2,9}, Susana Vázquez Torres^{1,2,9}, Anna Lauko^{1,2,9}, Valentin De Bortoli⁸, Emile Mathieu¹⁰, Sergey Ovchinnikov^{11,12}, Regina Barzilay⁶, Tommi S. Jaakkola⁶, Frank DiMaio^{1,2}, Minkyung Baek¹³ & David Baker^{1,2,14}✉

PROTEIN DESIGN

Robust deep learning–based protein sequence design using ProteinMPNN

J. Dauparas^{1,2}, I. Anishchenko^{1,2}, N. Bennett^{1,2,3}, H. Bai^{1,2,4}, R. J. Ragotte^{1,2}, L. F. Milles^{1,2}, B. I. M. Wicky^{1,2}, A. Courbet^{1,2,4}, R. J. de Haas⁵, N. Bethel^{1,2,4}, P. J. Y. Leung^{1,2,3}, T. F. Huddy^{1,2}, S. Pellock^{1,2}, D. Tischer^{1,2}, F. Chan^{1,2}, B. Koepnick^{1,2}, H. Nguyen^{1,2}, A. Kang^{1,2}, B. Sankaran⁶, A. K. Bera^{1,2}, N. P. King^{1,2}, D. Baker^{1,2,4,*}

Although deep learning has revolutionized protein structure prediction, almost all experimentally characterized de novo protein designs have been generated using physically based approaches such as Rosetta. Here, we describe a deep learning–based protein sequence design method, ProteinMPNN, that has outstanding performance in both in silico and experimental tests. On native protein backbones, ProteinMPNN has a sequence recovery of 52.4% compared with 32.9% for Rosetta. The amino acid sequence at different positions can be coupled between single or multiple chains, enabling application to a wide range of current protein design challenges. We demonstrate the broad utility and high accuracy of ProteinMPNN using x-ray crystallography, cryo-electron microscopy, and functional studies by rescuing previously failed designs, which were made using Rosetta or AlphaFold, of protein monomers, cyclic homo-oligomers, tetrahedral nanoparticles, and target-binding proteins.

IN SILICO ChuA BINDER DESIGN AND SELECTION

Design Parameters

- Backbone Design = RFDiffusion
- Sequence Generation = ProteinMPNN
- Filtering and Validation = AlphaFold2

~ **20,000 binders generated in silico**

- *AlphaFold2 confidence score screening*
 - *PAE Interaction < 10, and pLDDT > 90)*

~ **400 binders short listed**

Manual curation based on multiple criteria

**96 binders selected for gene synthesis by TWIST
BIOSCIENCE for wet lab screening**

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

ChuA BINDER GENE SYNTHESIS – TWIST BIOSCIENCE

96 ChuA Binders as amino acid sequence – length 70 to 120 AA

↓
*CODON ASSIGNMENT FOR E. coli EXPRESSION
(TWIST BIOSCIENCE WEB PORTAL)*

96 ChuA Binders as DNA Sequence

↓
*6xHis TAG TERMINUS ASSIGNMENT,
SEQUENCE PADDING to ≥ 300 bp,
VECTOR SELECTION*

96 ChuA Binder *E. coli* Expression Construct Sequences

↓
*ORDER PLACEMENT AT TWIST BIOSCIENCE,
DNA SYNTHESIS, SHIPPING*

96-well plate containing ChuA Binder Expression DNA Constructs
(Ordered 16th Feb – Received 7th March 2024)

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

ChuA BINDER HIGH-THROUGHPUT EXPRESSION + PURIFICATION

96-well plate containing ChuA Binder Expression DNA Constructs

↓ *TRANSFORM CONSTRUCTS INTO E. coli EXPRESSION STRAIN
IN 96-WELL PLATE FORMAT.
ANTIBIOTIC SELECTION IN WELL, NO PLATING OR COLONY SELECTION*

96-well plate containing *E. coli* expression strain for each binder

↓ *PARALLEL 24-WELL PLATE EXPRESSION OF ALL 96 BINDERS.
OVERNIGHT AUTO-INDUCTION BROTH,
IN-PLATE CELL MASS HARVESTING BY CENTRIFUGE*

E. coli cell pellets containing each of the 96 ChuA binders

↓ *CHEMICAL LYSIS OF CELLS IN 24 WELL PLATE FORMAT
CLARIFIED LYSATE TRANSFER TO 96-WELL PLATE
PARALELL ISOLATION OF ChuA BINDERS IN 96 WELL PLATE*

96-well plate containing (semi-)purified ChuA Binders
(DNA to protein in ~3 days)

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

SCREENING FOR SUCCESSFUL ChuA INHIBITORS

Daniel Fox

0.17 mg/ml Hemoglobin
0.125 mg/ml Hemin

SDS-PAGE semi-purified AI-Designed Binders

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

CHARACTERISING SUCCESSFUL ChuA INHIBITORS

Daniel Fox

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

CHARACTERISING SUCCESSFUL ChuA INHIBITORS

Daniel Fox

***100 nM Hemoglobin**

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

CHARACTERISING SUCCESSFUL ChuA INHIBITORS

Daniel Fox

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

ChuA BINDER STRUCTURE CLOSELY MATCHES DESIGNS

Daniel Fox

C8 crystals

*RMSD 0.55 Å
(721 of 952 atoms)*

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

ChuA BINDER STRUCTURE CLOSELY MATCHES DESIGNS

Daniel Fox

ChuA Apo

ChuA
+ Binder G7

ChuA
+ Binder H3

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

ChuA BINDER STRUCTURE CLOSELY MATCHES DESIGNS

Daniel Fox

*G7 RMSD = 0.63 Å
(743 of 1002 atoms)*

*H3 RMSD = 0.64 Å
(672 of 842 atoms)*

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

ChuA BINDERS BLOCK HEMOGLOBIN BY STERIC HINDERANCE

Daniel Fox

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

WHAT' NEXT FOR THIS PROJECT?

- Generate binders to other second heme transporter in pathogenic *E. coli* – Hma
- Assess efficacy of ChuA/HmA binders in mouse model of uropathogenic *E. coli* infection.
 - A fitness defect is observed in a *E. coli* ChuA/Hma double knockout in this model
 - This will provide valuable data on immunogenicity etc.

SETTING UP BINDER DESIGN FOR MY TARGET...

STAGE 0 – Access/establish a computational pipeline for AI-driven Binder design:

- It's possible to run AI-binder design packages online via Co-lab, but available compute is generally insufficient for full binder generation campaign. *Sustained access to 2-8 GPUs with ≥ 24 GB of VRAM is usually required. NVIDIA GPUs required!*
- We use a combination of local compute (lab server) and the University HPC clusters (e.g. Spartan). **Lab server for design scoping, HPC for large scale generation as required.**
 - *Don't be afraid of consumer grade GPU hardware but be aware of VRAM limitations for larger jobs and BindCraft.*
- National online pipelines are being developed via Galaxy.
- Pipelines can be implemented via cloud computing services (AWS, Azure, GCP etc.). These require some additional computer systems knowledge.

Our 2024 AI-design lab server specifications

Component	Specification
CPU	Intel Xeon W7-3465X (28 cores, 56 threads)
GPU	2 × NVIDIA RTX 4090 (24GB each)
RAM	256GB DDR5 ECC (8×32GB)
Storage	4TB NVMe SSD (2×2TB) + 8TB SSD + 20TB HDD
Total Cost (ex. GST)	AUD \$19,952.73

SETTING UP BINDER DESIGN FOR MY TARGET...

STAGE 0 – Access/establish a computational pipeline for AI-driven Binder design:

- Some packages/pipelines for de novo binder design:
 - **RFdiffusion-MPNN-AF2-initial guess (2023)**
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-023-06415-8>
<https://github.com/RosettaCommons/RFdiffusion>
https://github.com/nrbennet/dl_binder_design

BindCraft (2024)

<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2024.09.30.615802v2.full>
<https://github.com/martinpacesa/BindCraft>

- **Alphaproteo (2024; Not publicly available)**
<https://deepmind.google/discover/blog/alphaproteo-generates-novel-proteins-for-biology-and-health-research/>
- **Chai-2 (2025; Not publicly available)**
<https://www.chaidiscovery.com/news/introducing-chai-2>

BindCraft

bioRxiv
THE PREPRINT SERVER FOR BIOLOGY

HOME | SUI

New Results

Follow this preprint

BindCraft: one-shot design of functional protein binders

Martin Pacesa, Lennart Nickel, Christian Schellhaas, Joseph Schmidt, Ekaterina Pyatova, Lucas Kissling, Patrick Barendse, Jagrity Choudhury, Srajan Kapoor, Ana Alcaraz-Serna, Yehlin Cho, Kourosh H. Ghamary, Laura Vinue, Brahm J. Yachnin, Andrew M. Wollacott, Stephen Buckley, Adrie H Westphal, Simon Lindhoud, Sandrine Georgeon, Casper A. Goverde, Georgios N. Hatzopoulos, Pierre Gonczy, Yannick D. Muller, Gerald Schwank, Daan C Swarts, Alex J Vecchio, Bernard L Schneider, Sergey Ovchinnikov, Bruno E. Correia

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.09.30.615802>

This article is a preprint and has not been certified by peer review [what does this mean?].

BindCraft (2024)

<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2024.09.30.615802v2.full>

<https://github.com/martinpacesa/BindCraft>

- Open source, no-commercial restrictions
- Experimental success rates 10-100%
- Higher GPU VRAM required
- Slow with systems >400 amino acids

Alphaproteo

RESEARCH

AlphaProteo generates novel proteins for biology and health research

5 SEPTEMBER 2024

Protein Design and Wet Lab teams

← Share

- Alphaproteo (2024)
<https://deepmind.google/discover/blog/alphaproteo-generates-novel-proteins-for-biology-and-health-research/>
- Not publicly available/closed source, restrictions for commercial use.
- Reported experimental success rates of 0.3-88%

Chai-2

Chai Discovery

- Chai-2 (2025)
<https://www.chaidiscovery.com/news/introducing-chai-2>
- Not publicly available/closed source
- Reported experimental success rates of:
 - 68% for de novo mini binders
 - 16% for de novo antibodies (against 50% of targets)

SETTING UP BINDER DESIGN FOR MY TARGET...

STAGE 0 – Access/Establish a computational pipeline for AI-driven Binder design:

- Implementing RFDiffusion/BindCraft on a cluster or lab server requires some experience with Linux, Bash, Python, and Conda, or some upskilling, but you don't need to be an expert.
- The process will be **FRUSTURATING!**, at least initially. Some tips from my experience:
 - *For a lab server **Lambda Stack** is useful for automatically installing and updating AI software, from PyTorch to CUDA.*
 - *Carefully reviewing documentation on GitHub pages is helpful.*
 - *Using ChatGPT etc. to troubleshoot issues and generate simple code/scripts is hugely enabling.*
 - *Tenacity in troubleshooting and reaching out to developers and the community for advice is important. There will be a solution to your error/bug.*
- **You don't need a sophisticated pipeline to get good results!**

<https://lambda.ai/lambda-stack-deep-learning-software>

SETTING UP BINDER DESIGN FOR MY TARGET...

STAGE 1– Binder design using your installed pipeline:

- Identify target for binder design campaign:
 - Select **experimental structure** ($<2.5 \text{ \AA}$, stable B-factors in targeted region) or generate **computational model** of target (high confidence in targeted region e.g. $>90 \text{ pLDDT score}$)
- Trim model to smallest size that includes the target region.
 - VRAM and runtimes scale at roughly N^2 with residue count.
 - Beware of 'binder escape' to the exposed hydrophobic core.
- Identify target region for the binder on target structure.
 - Select a number of 'hotspot' residues to tell the pipeline where to generate the binder.

SETTING UP BINDER DESIGN FOR MY TARGET...

STAGE 1– Binder design using your installed pipeline

- Integrating as much information about the target at this stage is critical. For example:
 - Different conformational states
 - Post-translational modifications
 - Cellular localization
 - Functional regions
 - Biological mechanism/intended function of binder
- Once optimal design parameters have been identified scale up binder generation to generate final set of designs. We aim for:
 - *200-400 RFDiffusion designs passing in silico metrics (PAE_interact <10, pLDDT >90)*
 - *50-100 BindCraft designs (passing automatic quality metrics)*
 - *This will generally take days to a month of GPU time.*
- We further curate these binders for fold diversity, interaction interface, binding energy, fold etc. **Unclear how useful these filters are.**

SETTING UP BINDER DESIGN FOR MY TARGET...

STAGE 2– Binder synthesis and screening

- We generally screen **96 binders for Rfdiffusion** and **24-48 binders from BindCraft**. This is based on published and in house success rates.
- We use **TWIST Biosciences** to synthesize binder DNA as clonal genes in expression vectors.
 - Approximately \$70-100 per binder
 - NGS verified, rapid synthesis and delivery
 - Cloning from gene blocks is possible, but this isn't a cost/time effective solution.
- Use previously described small scale parallel protein expression platform to produce binders.
 - Generally, this achieves ~80-90% binder expression
 - ~100-500ug of binder, which is sufficient for identifying good binders.

SETTING UP BINDER DESIGN FOR MY TARGET...

STAGE 2 – Binder synthesis and screening

- Perform initial screen of binders for target affinity and activity. Our philosophy is to use whatever assay(s) give the fastest result with the least effort.
 - The aim with this stage is to identify several good binders, qualitative/semiquantitative is OK.
 - Bio-layer interferometry (BLI is a good compromise between throughput and quantification)
 - Cell based functional or binding assays are great.
 - Cross correlation between two methods is useful but not essential
- This pipeline/methodology is not the only way of screening binders you imitation is the limit. E.g.
 - Selection of binders from pooled libraries in cells
 - Intracellular expression of discrete binder libraries
 - In vitro translation combined with enzyme assays

SETTING UP BINDER DESIGN FOR MY TARGET...

STAGE 2– Binder synthesis and screening

- Scale up expression of the best performing binders from the initial screen for rigorous characterization.
 - Quantify binder affinity and activity
 - **Structural Characterisation of Complex?**
- Binder affinity/activity can be optimized using experimental (e.g. **Phage-display**) or computational maturation (e.g. **Partial diffusion**)
- Characterize binders for suitability for downstream/therapeutic use, assess:
 - Stability
 - Toxicity to mammalian cells
 - Immunogenicity

This is the next stage in the process for us, worth preserving a diversity of designs for testing at this stage.

Stage 1: De novo Protein Binder Generation

Stage 2: De novo Binder Screening and Development

What's next for AI-guided protein binder design? – Challenges

Target site selection limitations

- Developing binders to polar and flat proteins surfaces is still difficult
- Explicitly accounting for post-translational modifications still difficult

Experimental success rates

- We achieved ~4% success rate with nM affinity, against ChuA, which is OK.
- BindCraft etc. achieve significantly higher success rates
- Improved experimental success rates will improve economics (DNA synthesis/ screening costs)

Fox et al. Nat Comms. (2025)

What's next for AI-guided protein binder design? – Challenges

Limited pool of researchers have the required skillset

- A deep understanding of protein biochemistry and structural biology required

And

- Skills and understanding of machine learning and computer systems required for best results (and for development)

De novo antibodies still difficult

- Antibodies are the easiest modality to translate rapidly into therapeutics.
- ML based structure prediction still struggles with predicted protein antibody complexes, although this is improving.
- Chai-2 looks like a significant advance in this area, but not (yet) readily available to the community.

Fox et al FEBS letters (2024)

What's next for AI-guided protein binder design? – Challenges

Bioavailability and delivery

- Oral bioavailability may be possible
- mRNA delivery for some targets
- Inhalation or injection would work in some cases

Stability, Toxicity and Immunogenicity

- Much work still required remain but initial indications are positive
- Binders are highly thermostable and resistant to proteases, which should help with this

Cell

CellPress
OPEN ACCESS

Article

Preclinical proof of principle for orally delivered Th17 antagonist miniproteins

Stephanie Berger,^{1,2,16,*} Franziska Seeger,^{1,2} Ta-Yi Yu,^{1,2,3} Merve Aydin,⁴ Huilin Yang,^{5,6} Daniel Rosenblum,⁷ Laure Guenin-Macé,^{7,8} Caleb Glassman,⁹ Lauren Arguinchona,^{1,2} Catherine Sniezek,² Alyssa Blackstone,² Lauren Carter,² Rashmi Ravichandran,² Maggie Ahlrichs,² Michael Murphy,² Ingrid Swanson Pultz,² Alex Kang,^{1,2} Asim K. Bera,^{1,2} Lance Stewart,² K. Christopher Garcia,^{9,10,11} Shruti Naik,^{7,12} Jamie B. Spangler,^{5,6,13} Florian Beigel,¹⁴ Matthias Siebeck,⁴ Roswitha Gropp,⁴ and David Baker^{1,2,15,*}

¹Department of Biochemistry, University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98195, USA

²Institute for Protein Design, University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98195, USA

³Department of Bioengineering, University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98195, USA

⁴Department of General, Visceral and Transplantation Surgery, LMU University Hospital, LMU Munich, 81377 Munich, Germany

⁵Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD 21218, USA

⁶Translational Tissue Engineering Center, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD 21231, USA

⁷Department of Pathology, NYU Langone Health, New York, NY 10016, USA

⁸Immunobiology and Therapy Unit, INSERM U1224, Institut Pasteur, Paris 75015, France

⁹Department of Molecular and Cellular Physiology, Stanford University School of Medicine, Stanford, CA 94304, USA

¹⁰Department of Structural Biology, Stanford University School of Medicine, Stanford, CA 94304, USA

¹¹Howard Hughes Medical Institute, Stanford School of Medicine, Stanford, CA 94305, USA

¹²Department of Medicine, Ronald O. Perleman Department of Dermatology, Perlmutter Cancer Center, NYU Langone Health, New York, NY 10016, USA

¹³Department of Biomedical Engineering, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD 21218, USA

¹⁴Department of Medicine II, LMU University Hospital, LMU Munich, 80336 Munich, Germany

¹⁵Howard Hughes Medical Institute, University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98195, USA

¹⁶Lead contact

*Correspondence: berger389@gmail.com (S.B.), dabaker@uw.edu (D.B.)

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2024.05.052>

What's next for AI-guided protein binder design? – Challenges

Bioavailability and delivery

- Oral bioavailability may be possible
- mRNA delivery for some targets
- Inhalation or injection would work in some cases

Stability, Toxicity and Immunogenicity

- Much work still required remain but initial indications are positive
- Binders are highly thermostable and resistant to proteases, which should help with this

Article

De novo designed proteins neutralize lethal snake venom toxins

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-08393-x>

Received: 8 May 2024

Accepted: 13 November 2024

Published online: 15 January 2025

Open access

 Check for updates

Susana Vázquez Torres^{1,2,3}, Melisa Benard Valle⁴, Stephen P. Mackessy⁵, Stefanie K. Menzies^{6,7,8}, Nicholas R. Casewell^{6,7}, Shirin Ahmadi⁴, Nick J. Burtlet⁴, Edin Muratspahić^{1,2}, Isaac Sappington^{1,2,3}, Max D. Overath⁴, Esperanza Rivera-de-Torre⁴, Jann Ledergerber⁴, Andreas H. Laustsen⁴, Kim Boddum⁹, Asim K. Bera^{1,2}, Alex Kang^{1,2}, Evans Brackenbrough^{1,2}, Iara A. Cardoso⁶, Edouard P. Crittenden⁶, Rebecca J. Edge¹⁰, Justin Decarreau^{1,2}, Robert J. Ragotte^{1,2}, Arvind S. Pillai^{1,2}, Mohamad Abedi^{1,2}, Hannah L. Han^{1,2}, Stacey R. Gerben^{1,2}, Analisa Murray^{1,2}, Rebecca Skotheim^{1,2}, Lynda Stuart^{1,2}, Lance Stewart^{1,2}, Thomas J. A. Fryer^{4,11}, **Timothy P. Jenkins**⁴✉ & David Baker^{1,2,12}✉

Snakebite envenoming remains a devastating and neglected tropical disease, claiming over 100,000 lives annually and causing severe complications and long-lasting disabilities for many more^{1,2}. Three-finger toxins (3FTx) are highly toxic components of elapid snake venoms that can cause diverse pathologies, including severe tissue damage³ and inhibition of nicotinic acetylcholine receptors, resulting in life-threatening neurotoxicity⁴. At present, the only available treatments for snakebites consist of polyclonal antibodies derived from the plasma of immunized animals, which have high cost and limited efficacy against 3FTxs⁵⁻⁷. Here we used deep learning methods to de novo design proteins to bind short-chain and long-chain α -neurotoxins and cytotoxins from the 3FTx family. With limited experimental screening, we obtained protein designs with remarkable thermal stability, high binding affinity and near-atomic-level agreement with the computational models. The designed proteins effectively neutralized all three 3FTx subfamilies in vitro and protected mice from a lethal neurotoxin challenge. Such potent, stable and readily manufacturable toxin-neutralizing proteins could provide the basis for safer, cost-effective and widely accessible next-generation antivenom therapeutics. Beyond snakebite, our results highlight how computational design could help democratize therapeutic discovery, particularly in resource-limited settings, by substantially reducing costs and resource requirements for the development of therapies for neglected tropical diseases.

AUSTRALIAN PROTEIN DESIGN INITIATIVE

Dr Gavin Knott

Dr Marija Dramicanin

Ramaciotti Centre for
Cryo-Electron Microscopy

Hari Venugopal
Bradley Spicer
Chris Lupton

Australian Government
Australian Research Council

Indicators of the potential of this technology

